

**RAPID REVIEW PROTOCOL:
Technology Probe of Software Technologies
May - 2024**

1. Scenario

Technology Probe (TP) is a collaborative method between users and developers to create new technologies. This method requires a Probe (functional prototype) to be installed in the user's environment, allowing the developers to collect their perceptions and improve the Probe. These collected data are evaluated regarding three aspects [Hutchinson et al. 2003]: (i) social, focusing on user interaction with the probe; (ii) engineer, focusing on the technology or manufacturing; (iii) design, identifying opportunities for innovation.

Even though TP seems a promising method to co-create technologies and evaluate software from a user perspective, it has a complication in its applicability. To use Technology Probe, the researcher must develop a technique, such as defining instruments to collect and analyse data. This research aims to map TP techniques developed in other studies. This way, it is possible to understand this field's state of the art and propose a unified approach for TP.

2. Goal and Research Question

a. Goal

The main goal of this research is to understand how studies used the Technology Probe method in order to identify techniques and instruments employed for the TP.

b. Research Question

Problem:

There is no standard for applying Technology Probe. The researcher is responsible for developing a technique for using it (participant/user profile, instruments to collect and analyse data..., etc.). Therefore, organising the knowledge regarding which TP techniques have already been developed and used is relevant for the evolution of this method.

Research Questions:

How is Technology Probe being used to evaluate software technologies?

What techniques or practices can be used to support the Technology Probe in software engineering?

3. Sources, Language e Research String

a. Source

This study will use the Scopus database, which integrates different libraries and provides diverse results from peer-reviewed scientific journals and conference

proceedings. Additionally, the snowballing (one step forward/backward) will be performed using the final selected papers from Scopus.

b. Language and Research String

The language chosen for the selection of work is "English". Regarding the search string, the expression was defined using the PICOC method [Petticrew & Roberts, 2006].

PICOC	STRING
<i>Population</i>	("software systems" OR "software engineering" OR "software" OR "systems" OR "applications" OR "solution" OR "platforms" OR "prototypes" OR "products" OR "MVP" OR "Minimum Viable Product" OR "technolog*") AND
<i>Intervention</i>	("technology probe" OR "lean cycle" OR "build-measure-learn" OR "continuous experimentation with customers") AND
<i>Comparison</i>	-
<i>Outcome</i>	("technique" OR "method" OR "evaluation" OR "approach" OR "process" OR "tool*" OR "procedure" OR "strategy" OR "research" OR "study")
<i>Context</i>	-

The Scopus search string is: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("software systems" OR "software engineering" OR "software" OR "systems" OR "applications" OR "solution" OR "platforms" OR "prototypes" OR "products" OR "mvp" OR "minimum viable product" OR "technolog*") AND ("technology probe" OR "lean cycle" OR "build-measure-learn" OR "continuous experimentation with customers") AND ("technique" OR "method" OR "evaluation" OR "approach" OR "process" OR "tool*" OR "procedure" OR "strategy" OR "research" OR "study")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

4. Criteria

a. Inclusion Criteria

- To discuss a Technology Probe technique
- It is related to software technologies
- Peer-reviewed English text
- It is a primary study

b. Exclusion Criteria

- Full text is not available;

- Duplicated studies;
- It is a secondary study (e.g., another rapid review);
- Do not discuss a TP technique; only replicate one (use snowballing to get the work that proposes the technique)
- Chapter Books and reviews

5. Data Extraction

a. Modelo de Extração

A) Papers Data:	
Title:	work title
Author(s):	authors name
Source:	Where it was published
Year:	publication year
Abstract:	work abstract
B) Data based on the Goal:	
Motivation	motivation to use technology probe
Probe	what was the software technology solution used
Technique	description of the technique or practice proposed in the work
Outcomes	conclusions from the Technology Probe
Advantages of the Technique (optional)	what were the advantages of using the described technique
Disadvantages of the Technique (optional)	what were the disadvantages of using the described technique

6. Update (December/24)

On 18/December/24 the search was done again. It returned 287 documents (having 24 extra papers). This papers will be submitted to the same filter the other one had

7. References

Hutchinson, H., Mackay, W., Westerlund, B., Bederson, B. B., Druin, A., Plaisant, C., Beaudouin-Lafon, M., Conversy, S., Evans, H., Hansen, H., et al. (2003). Technology probes: inspiring design for and with families. In Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems, pages 17–24

Petticrew, Mark and Helen Roberts. Systematic Reviews in the Social Sciences: A Practical Guide. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd, 2006, doi:10.1002/9780470754887.